

Effect of Melatonin Pretreatment on Nephrotoxicity Induced by Ampicillin Sodium in Wild Tropical Rodent, Indian Palm Squirrel, *F. pennanti*.

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Running Title: Nephrotoxicity by Ampicilline sodium

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Introduction:

It has been speculated that primary function of melatonin may include protecting organisms from intrinsically or environmentally induced oxidative stress. A large number of publications have shown that melatonin detoxifies a variety of oxidants including OH, O₂, NO, ONOO, HOCl, the hemoglobin oxo-ferryl radical and possibly (Acuna-Castroviejo et al., 2001; Turjanski et al., 2001; Stasica et al., 2000) there by , reducing oxidative damage both under in vitro and in vivo conditions (Vural et al., 2001; Yamamoto and Mohanan, 2001; . Fulia et al., 2001).

Oxidative stress and antioxidant defense One of the factors that plays a major role in many pathological situations including cancer, ischemia/reperfusion injury, neurodegenerative disorders and even aging, is the excessive generation of free radicals (Kehrer, 1993; Knight, 1998). Free radicals are molecules which contain an unpaired number of electrons in their valence orbital; this makes them highly unstable and thus extraordinarily reactive. Among these agents are reactive oxygen species (ROS) which react and damage essential molecules within the cells including lipids, proteins and DNA (de Groot, 1994; Toyokuni, 1999). In conditions where there is excessive ROS, the resulting molecular destruction is identified as oxidative damage (Pierrefiche and Laborit, 1995). Reactive oxygen species are formed naturally during many metabolic processes and, thus, cells have developed diverse mechanisms to reduce the deleterious consequences of ROS. To protect themselves against ROS, cells have developed an antioxidant defense which includes enzymatic and non enzymatic mechanisms. ROS and the antioxidant defense must be in perfect equilibrium to avoid that the relation between ROS formation and depuration being unbalanced. Enzymes involved in the elimination of ROS include superoxide dismutases (SOD), catalase (CAT) and glutathione peroxidase (GPx). Besides the enzymatic antioxidant system, there are non enzymatic antioxidants, or free radical scavengers, which remove ROS directly because of their electron donating ability thereby neutralizing potential ROS toxicity. The best known nonenzymatic antioxidants are vitamin E (a-tocopherol), vitamin C (ascorbate), glutathione (GSH), b-carotene, and more recently, melatonin. Melatonin: role on oxidative stress regulation the main pineal product, melatonin (N-acetyl-5-methoxytryptamine), functions as time-giver (Zeitgeber) in the regulation of circadian rhythms (Arendt, 2003) and in synchronizing the reproductive cycle with the appropriate season of the year in photoperiodic species (Reiter, 1980). In non photoperiodic species such as humans, the melatonin's actions are restricted to other functions of the circadian

clock, i.e. consolidation of sleep and regulation of the circadian rhythm of core body temperature (Turek and Gillette, 2004). Melatonin's actions, however, are not restricted to its role in the neuroendocrine physiology. Since 1993, melatonin has been known as a radical scavenger with the ability to remove ROS including singlet oxygen (1O_2), superoxide anion radical (O_2^-), hydroperoxide (H_2O_2), hydroxyl radical ($OH\bullet$) and the lipid peroxide radical ($LOO\bullet$) (Tan et al., 1993; Hardeland et al., 1993; Tan et al., 2002; Allegra et al., 2003). In some cases, melatonin's efficacy exceeds that of GSH and vitamin E, which are well known antioxidants (Tan et al., 1993; Hardeland et al., 1993). Melatonin's ability to counteract ROS has special relevance as it crosses all morphophysiological barriers and it is widely distributed in tissues, cells and sub cellular compartments, because of its distinct physical and chemical properties (Costa et al., 1997; Ceraulo, 1999). These allow its localization in cellular organelles and in the cytosol, cellular membranes and nucleus (Costa et al., 1997; Menendez-Pelaez et al., 1993; Menendez-Pelaez and Reiter, 1993; Coto-Montes et al., 1996). Its widespread sub cellular distribution guarantees its ability to interact with toxic molecules throughout the cell, thereby reducing oxidative damage to molecules in both the lipid and aqueous environments of the cells (Karbownik and Reiter, 2000; Yamamoto and Mohanan, 2003). Melatonin also acts as an indirect antioxidant through the activation of the major antioxidant enzymes including SOD, CAT, and GPx (Barlow-Walden et al., 1995; Pablos et al., 1998; Antolin et al., 1996; Tomas-Zapico et al., 2002). This activation is a consequence of antioxidant enzyme mRNA synthesis and eventually enzyme stimulation. These processes probably involve melatonin receptors (Pablos et al., 1998; Mayo et al., 2002; Coto-Montes et al., 2003), although this remains unknown. Several species melatonin receptors have been described in a large variety of mammalian and non mammalian cell types. These include two members of the group of the membrane G-protein-coupled receptors, designated as mt1 and MT2 (Reppert et al., 1994; Reppert et al., 1995). Furthermore, the effect of melatonin on transcriptional regulation clearly depend on the expression of RZR/ROR receptors which are located in the nucleus and support the concept that these receptors are mediators of nuclear melatonin signaling (Wiesenberg et al., 1998). Likewise, the coexistence of mt1 and RORa1 receptor has been reported in immune system cells and several other organs (Coto-Montes et al., 2003; Carrillo-Vico et al., 2003; Naji et al., 2004) and in several cell lines (Ram et al., 2002; Karasek et al., 2002).

Experimental setup:

Group I: Control

Seven adult male squirrels were kept in natural environmental condition (Control) as mentioned above without any treatment.

Group II: Ampicillin treated (ampi)

Seven adult male squirrels were kept in natural environmental condition as mentioned above. A single dose of intravenous injection (through subclavian vein) of Ampicillin sodium (40mg/Kg body wt.) reconstituted in triple distilled water was given every day between 10:30 am and 11:00 am as mentioned in material & method.

Group III: Melatonin treated (mel)

Seven adult male squirrels were kept in natural environmental condition as mentioned above. Melatonin (100 μ g /kg body weight) was injected subcutaneously every day between 5:00 to 5:30 pm (i.e. half hour before sunset).

Group IV: Ampicillin + Melatonin (ampi+mel)

Seven adult male squirrels were kept in natural environmental condition as mentioned above. A single dose of intravenous injection (through subclavian vein) of Ampicillin sodium (40mg/Kg body wt.) reconstituted in triple distilled water was given every day between 10:30

am and 11:00 am and Melatonin (100µg /kg body weight) was injected subcutaneously every day between 5:00 to 5:30 pm (i.e. half hour before sunset).

Parameters Assayed:

All the treatments were given for seven days and on the eighth day that is after 24 hours of last treatments animals were decapitated. The bladder was surgically extruded and emptied by supra-pubic puncture. This procedure ensured collection of urine produced over a period of 60 min. At the time of sacrifice, thus urine was collected, and its volume was measured and biochemical parameters ACP, ALP, Creatinine and Urea were estimated. After removal of both kidneys through a midline abdominal incision, the right and left kidneys were processed. The kidneys were stripped from their capsule, weighed, and slit by longitudinal incision. Cortical, medullary (outer medulla), and papillary (inner medulla-papillary tip) components were separated under a dissecting microscope. The accuracy of the dissection was verified by light microscopy. Renal cortical tissue homogenates were prepared separately (as mentioned in materials and methods) for the detection of Superoxide dismutase activity (SOD), lipid peroxidation level (TBARS) and Total antioxidant status (TAS %). Trunk Blood was collected in separate centrifuge tubes and blood/plasma was taken for biochemical estimations that are BUN, ACP, ALP, and Creatinine with Total kidney cortical protein.

Statistical analysis:

All the data were expressed as means \pm SEM of at least five animals per group. Data comparisons were statistically analyzed by using ANOVA followed by Student Newman-Keuls' multiple range tests. The differences were considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$ (Bruning and Knitz, 1977). Microsoft Excel program was used for statistical calculations.

Result

Fig. 1

Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500µg/Kg body wt) on Acid phosphatase (ACP) in (A) blood, (B) urine and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) in (C) blood, (D) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference ** $p < 0.001$; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (ampi), Melatonin treated (mel) and Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (mel+ampi) groups.

Fig 2

Fig. 2

Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500µg/Kg body wt) on blood urea nitrogen (BUN), urine urea (B) and creatinine in blood (C) urine (D) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference ** p<0.001; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (ampi), Melatonin treated (mel) and Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (mel+ampi) groups.

Fig 3

Fig. 3

(A) Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500µg/Kg body wt) on the total kidney cortical protein weight of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference ** p<0.001; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (ampi), Melatonin treated (mel) and Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (mel+ampi) groups.

(B) Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500µg/Kg body wt) on the malon-dialdehyde level (TBARS) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference ** p<0.001; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (ampi), Melatonin treated (mel) and Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (mel+ampi) groups.

(C) Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500µg/Kg body wt) on the total antioxidative status (TAS %) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference ** p<0.001; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (ampi), Melatonin treated (mel) and Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (mel+ampi) groups.

(D) Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500µg/Kg body wt) on super oxide-dismutase activity (SOD) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference ** p<0.001; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (ampi), Melatonin treated (mel) and Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (mel+ampi) groups.

Increase in alkaline phosphatase, acid phosphatase, creatinin and urea in urine as well as in blood following Ampicillin treatment indicates the direct toxic effects of Ampicillin on the above parameters when compared to controls and combined treated (ampicillin+melatonin) groups. Lipid per oxidation level (TBARS) was found significantly high in Ampicillin treated groups, when compared with controls and combined treated groups. The reason of such effects could be due to the oxidative stress i.e. free radical load induced by Ampicillin metabolism which was minimized by combined treatment with melatonin where melatonin might be acting (directly or indirectly) to reduce the free radical load significantly but not to the control levels.

Cytosolic protein levels of kidney cortical region were significantly high in Ampicillin treated groups when compared with the controls and combined treated ones. The new proteins would have been synthesized to adapt the degradation caused by Ampicillin and the proteins from membrane might have mobilized in the cytosol due to lipid peroxidation. Combined treatment with melatonin completely stopped the above effects. The total antioxidative status (TAS %) increased following the Ampicillin treatment may be due to high free radical generation by Ampicillin toxicity (metabolism). To combat this free radical load, antioxidative enzymes would have increased their activity more or some extra antioxidative enzyme might have been produced following melatonin treatment. Combined treatment reduced the antioxidative status but not to the control levels. This implies that melatonin treatment (dose & duration) provided by us was not sufficient enough to reduce the free radical load (directly/indirectly) due to which the total antioxidative status could not reach to the level of controls. Ampicillin treatment reduced the SOD activity below the control levels indicating presence/involvement of less super oxide radicals, which also indicates that the Ampicillin toxicity is not mediated / caused by SOD radicals. But why combined treatment increased SOD activity is not clear. It could be that Hydroxyl radicals (OH) are being affected by Ampicillin and it will be the next target of the study. Result clearly indicates that Ampicillin is causing nephrotoxicity by inducing free radical load probably other than superoxide (SOD) radicals. Melatonin can ameliorate the nephrotoxicity induced by Ampicillin to some extent but not completely. Since the results are of high clinical value further dose dependent studies are in progress. There are some experimental data suggesting that nephrotoxic drugs may also change

levels of MDA, GSH, BUN, and Cr (Ozbek et al., 2000; Sener et al., 2002; Parlakpınar et al., 2002), which are commonly used to monitor the development and extent of renal tubular damage due to oxidative stress. It has also been reported that the light and electron microscopic assessments were more sensitive than the other methods in determining toxicity (Klein et al., 1992).

Plate 1

Histomicrograph of squirrel kidney cortical region showing Glomerulus (G), increased capsular space (→), affected brush bordered vesicular epithelial cells (BBVEC) (*) of proximal convoluted tubule (PCT), distal convoluted tubule (DCT), loop of henle and collecting tubule. (Under 40X objective)

- A- Control (control)
- B- Ampicillin treated (ampi)
- C- Melatonin treated (mel)
- D- Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (mel+ampi)

Aminoglycosides are not metabolized in the body, and most of the injected dose is excreted through urine, whereas a fraction accumulates in the renal proximal tubule cells, where the concentration of aminoglycosides is several times higher than in the plasma. The concentrated accumulation of aminoglycosides in the proximal tubule cells is associated with nephrotoxicity (Humes, 1988). In addition to scavenging free radicals such as the hydroxyl radical, singlet oxygen, peroxy radical, and the peroxy nitrite anion, melatonin also reduces their generation (Humes, 1988; Acuna-Castroviejo et al., 2001). Additionally, the antioxidant actions of melatonin probably derive from its stimulatory effect on superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px), glutathione reductase (GSH-Rd), and glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase, and its inhibitory action on nitric oxide synthase (Reiter et al., 1998). Melatonin is lipophilic and passes easily through biological membranes (Vaughan and Reiter, 1986; Zanononi et al., 1978), providing an advantage over other antioxidants which penetrate cells more slowly. Probably the property of melatonin to rapidly enter cells would be an important feature in reducing ampicillin-induced toxicity. Although the retina has a high capacity for synthesizing melatonin, it does not seem to contribute significantly to the plasma melatonin concentrations probably because of rapid catabolism in the retina. Recent studies have shown that melatonin prevents the nephrotoxicity caused by several drugs. For example, melatonin reduced lipid peroxidation, serum BUN and Cr, and elevated GSH levels induced by renal ischemia reperfusion (Antolin et al., 1996) and nephrotoxic agents including cisplatin

(Arendt, 2003; Tomas-Zapico et al., 2002). In another study, melatonin was found to have a similar beneficial effect on MDA, GSH, BUN, Cr and histologic damage in combination with aminoglycoside antibiotics including gentamicin (Toyokuni, 1999; Pierrefiche and Laborit, 1995). Taking in to consideration the reduced oxidative damage caused by melatonin treatment, all investigators attributed the protective actions of melatonin to its direct and indirect antioxidative activity.

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